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Citizens Budget and Evaluating Citizens Budget in Turkey

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1. Introduction

Citizens Budget has become an important document to increase citizen involvement in budget process and to support transparency and clarity principles. As the citizens know where and what the government expenditure are, the ratio of involvement to the following budgeting process will increase.

Public Finance Management and Control Law with issue number 5018 classifies budgeting process into three categories such as financial transparency, accountability and accountability responsibility and performance auditing. From this point of view as the importance of budget transparency is emphasized, it can be concluded that transparency provided only for the experts is insufficient and citizens should be able to access general information and data. Therefore, in addition to documents with general budget information, it is important to form a simple and clear citizen budget for budget transparency so that the citizens can understand the general concept.

In this study, citizen budget concepts, importance and development of citizens budget are considered and citizens budget in Turkey is evaluated.

2. Citizens Budget Concept

Citizens Budget aims to provide citizen involvement in the budget process. Citizens Budget is a document that enables to share the budget with public opinion in a transparent, clear, and understandable way and thus increasing the involvement of citizens to the budget process. As public opinion on expense items in budget which directly affect citizens are included, citizens budget becomes more feasible. Involvement of citizens in budgeting will speed up democratic development process and thus increase transparency and accountability levels (Şeker and Beynam, 2013: 221-222).

Citizens Budget is a document that summarizes fundamental budget information. The document is a report that is simplified in terms of format and language so that the citizens can understand this document. The citizens desire an explanation for what the government has done on their behalf by asking democracy based questions. Primary beneficiary of Citizens Budget document is the citizens. Citizens Budget is a multi-purpose document that aims to increase current information of citizens on what the government actions are and what has been done to develop involvement to government activities (IBP Citizens Budget Guide, 2012: 9).

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3. Development and Importance of Citizens Budget

In the last 10 years, there are important developments in the financial management of the countries to publish Citizens Budgets. When 2012 data of International Budget Partnership (2012) that aims to measure budget transparency levels of countries with Open Budget Index is considered, it can be seen that 26 countries among 100 countries in the survey publish citizen budgets. These countries include high income countries such as Norway and New Zealand as well as middle income countries such as India, Croatia and Ghana (Şeker and Beynam, 2013: 223) . 2015 survey data evaluated 102 countries under this scope and it can be seen that 54 countries have published citizen budgets (IBP Full Report, 2015: 29). When the reports are evaluates, the change between 2012-2015 is striking.

Publishing a Citizens Budget guide enables to explain government budget aims and related budget talks using supplementary material such as press releases and internet pages in a simple and fluent language. It is vital that the information about the taxes collected by the government, government debts and expenditures are provided to the citizens (Petrie and Shields, 2010: 3).

4. Evaluating Citizens Budget in Turkey

Open Budget Survey conducted five times between 2006-2015 and related Open Budget Index publishes a report for all the countries included in the survey. The report published for Turkey made suggestions that citizen budget should be produced and published for transparency and development of public involvement (IBP Country Report, 2015: 2-3). Citizens budget concept has been first mentioned in Public Finance Management and Control Law issue number 5018, yet until 2017 there has not been any initiative. First work related with citizen budget concepts is published in 2017 under "Citizens Budget Guide". Since the Guide is the first application there are certain insufficient points in terms of content and scope, it can be considered as an important step in Turkish Budgeting process. This citizens budget document contains macroeconomic objectives as well as education, health, social assistance, investments, Research and Development, tourism, real sector supports, fees, tax incomes, tax expenditures and incentives and this documents presents data and objectives for the above mentioned subjects. Yet, citizens budget objective definition and budget process explanations are not provided. Including these explanations and terms in a field that requires economic literacy is important for the citizens to internalize the document and provide budget involvement. If we evaluate in a more specific way, Tax Amnesty Law issue number 6736 that become effective in 2016 is important in terms of collected income as well as expenditures, yet this data is not included. As public incentives for real sector are included sectoral performance objectives are excluded as well as employment, energy efficiency, production and consumptions subjects which can be evaluated as shortcomings of citizen budget guide. Additionally, if political processes and initiatives are included, citizen budget can be more meaningful (Vatandaş Bütçesi Rehberi, 2017).

5. Conclusion

"Citizens Budget" concept has become an important arguments in the last few years. Thus, the document has become an important sign of financial transparency as well as incentive for public involvement in budget process. In this context, it can be seen that until 2017, the proof

for any citizens budget cannot be observed in Turkey. Although prepared and published first citizens budget covers economy in a broader sense, the document is insufficient in terms of performance objectives data under sectoral scope. As macroeconomic indicators that are important for citizens are included, employment as the most important aspect of this subject is excluded from the document. Additionally there is a need for glossary of terms to explain economic terms or concepts other than budget definitions. Lastly, when citizens budget concept is explained to the citizens, it will be easier to understand this budget documents.

Keywords: Budget ,Citizens Budget, Open Budget Index

JEL Codes: H61, H11, H69

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